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Adverse effects framework (Version 1)

Mandatory fields are marked with a star *

Contact information

First and last name *

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This field was automatically filled in

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Objectives and criteria

The objectives of the framework are clear and meaningful. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The criteria for a sensible framework are clear and meaningful. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Framework and theoretical mechanisms

Before responding to the next item, please consider the first approach to theorising harms suggested by Bonell and colleagues: "reflecting on any possible unintended interactions between, on the one hand, the agency (willed actions) of providers [of an intervention], recipients and other stakeholders and, on the other, the social structures that enable and constrain this agency."

The framework includes all potential adverse effects that are relevant, logical, conceivable, and important. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The framework excludes all potential effects that are not adverse, or are irrelevant, illogical, inconceivable, or unimportant. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The structure, organisation and presentation of the framework are clear and logical. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The framework is as simple as possible without being oversimple. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The theoretical mechanisms are clear, logical, and consistent with any relevant evidence. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The framework provides a sensible starting point for a generic framework for preventing and evaluating potential adverse effects of critical thinking interventions. *

Please specify the degree to which you agree with the statement.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Please provide any references that can be used to build comparative understanding across similar interventions.

Other

Please provide any (other) references to relevant literature.

Please add any other comments or questions.

Send

Responsible for the form: maox@oslomet.no.